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THE USE OF HEURISTICS IN CONSUMER AND INVESTMENT SETTINGS: AN APPLICATION FOR MEMORY-BASED AND STIMULUS-BASED DECISIONS

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Abstract

Although they have some drawbacks, heuristics are effective tools for decision making. This paper focuses on the drivers of heuristic application regarding high involvement and low involvement decisions as well as memory-based and stimulus-based decisions. An online study carried out among 205 participants from 28 countries revealed significant differences for high and low involvement decisions regarding both the trade-off heuristic and the recognition heuristic. Moreover, memory-based and stimulus-based decisions were found not to differ in terms of the type of heuristics involved. We present and discuss several implications of these results for consumer and investment decisions. We include limitations of the study and suggestions for future research. This study intended to shed some light into the role of heuristics in decision making.

Keywords: Decision-Making; Heuristic; Memory-Based; Stimulus-Based; Involvement.

Introduction

Back in the 4th century BC, Plato stated that good decisions are based on knowledge and not on numbers. Although this approach might seem to deflate the importance of statistics and data, the quotation reveals the phenomenon of heuristics in decision taking processes applied in daily life of each human being. In contrary to a common view on heuristics, which assumes their negative biasing, this paper looks upon them as an efficient (and yet effective, albeit irrational) tool for decision making. This paper attempts to a better understanding of the processes our brains engage to make choices. More specifically, which heuristics are dominant and if their presence is desired for decisional outcomes. We also seek to understand if heuristics differ across different types of decision regarding engagement or exposure to stimuli. In view of above-mentioned

questions, the following study aims to bring value to consumer and managerial decision making, thus contributing to a more complex comprehension of choice-influencing factors.

Although both heuristics and explicit/implicit memory concepts are subject to many scientific studies, no research attempts to comprehend the relations between them. This paper analyses the link between heuristics and decision types, focusing on three main heuristics –recognition, one-variable and trade-off comparisons (Gigerenzer and Gaissmaier, 2011) –, using of which is collated between memory-based and stimulus-based choices (Lee, 2002; Rottenstreich, Sood, and Brenner, 2007). The frequency of use of the mentioned heuristic types significantly differs between memory-based and stimulus-based decisions, as well as low and high involvement decisions. In the next section (literature review), we intend to give an overview on relevant managerial and consumer decision making literature and the different approaches to heuristics.

Literature review

The phenomenon of decision making was a subject of philosophers' debate in Ancient Greece. Indeed, in the 5th century BC, Socrates already discussed the concept of rationality. Nevertheless, one can notice a growing interest in this field just in the middle of twentieth century, when it became a subject of more substantial psychological and managerial scientific research. Simon (1955) noticed that human cognition is limited compared to the complexity of the world and coined the term of bounded rationality, which in opposition to rationality describes the attempts of taking rational decision when dealing with time and cost constraints as well as limited (or low quality information) as well as intelligence limitations and perceptual errors (Asadullah and Kundi, 2013; Bazerman and Moore, 2013). This leads to the concept of satisficing (e.g., taking choices that achieve an acceptable and reasonable level of satisfaction rather than the optimal decision based on pure rationality). For example, Stiglitz (2010) considers satisficing a more efficient outcome than optimizing, from a resource-based perspective.

Researchers have discovered that human brain tends to apply simplified strategies when making decision in order to face above-mentioned limitations (Gigerenzer, 1991; Tversky and Kahneman, 1974; Raiffa, 1970). These strategies are described as heuristics – the term origins in Greek and means serving to find and discover. Shah and Oppenheimer (2008) focused on the effort reduction feature of heuristics, which may apply to the number of cues, retrieving cue values or their weights, integrating information and/or reducing the number of alternatives. Heuristics facilitate the achievement of satisficing outcomes more quickly, more frugally and more accurately (Gigerenzer and Gaissmaier, 2011).

The relevance of heuristics for decision making may be pre-justified by the less-can-be-more framework. To illustrate how complexity can hinder decisions, we will introduce the short research example of Wübben and Wangenheim (2008), in which a retailer tried to predict the customers who were likely to make a purchase in the future. In so doing, they simply analyzed whether a customer purchased any product within defined time period (one true-or-false variable), ignoring other cues such frequency of purchases or time spacing in-between them that would demand invoking complex statistical methods. This method was described as a hiatus heuristic and featured 3% to 8% more valid customer classifications compared to negative binominal distribution models, although additionally it reduced the decision effort.

The general application of heuristics can be justified by two fundamental concepts. The first one is the accuracy-effort trade-off (Payne, Bettman, and Johnson, 1993; Shah and Oppenheimer, 2008) and concerns with the acceptable loss of accuracy in favor of time and effort. The second one is the ecological rationality, coined by Gigerenzer (1991) and developed by Smith (2003), which suggests that heuristics are ecologically rational to the degree that they are adapted to the structure of the environment. In this research, we will assume heuristics as (positive) skills or abilities (conscious or subconscious) which help efficient (fast and frugal) decisions, as opposed to heuristics-as-biases (negative) framework.

However, we aim to sensitize the reader to possible negative effects of heuristics. Bazerman and Moore (2013) pointed out three main groups: (i) availability; (ii) representativeness; and (iii) confirmation. Availability heuristics simply focuses on decision biases caused by vividness, recallability, or memory structure. We shortly illustrate two examples which depict the phenomena. For instance, people typically underestimate the number of death caused by socially acceptable behaviors like tobacco smoking or poor diet and physical activity while overestimating the impact of guns or illicit drug use (Kahneman, Slovic, and Tversky, 1982). Also, insurance customers who experienced natural disaster are influenced by the recallability bias and tend to choose policy protecting from such events more frequently than customers who never experienced them (Kahneman et al., 1982).

There many biases emanating from representativeness heuristics. For instance, people tend to ignore sample size. Tversky and Kahneman (1974) asked respondents to judge in which maternity ward (that differed significantly regarding size) were recorded more days when 60% percent of boys were born. Respondents were given the information that on average 50% of newborns were boys; however the number varied from day to day. Most of respondents pointed out that the number of such days should be about the same, ignoring the statistical fact that smaller sample sizes tend to be more distant to population results. Other important representativeness biases consist in the conjunction fallacy, regression to mean and misconceptions of chance (Hardman, 2009). According to Bazerman and Moore (2013), the last big family of heuristic-based biases are composed of: (i) the confirmation trap – individuals tend to look for data which support their hypothesis while failing to find contradictory arguments); (ii) anchoring – making estimates based on given values ignoring their irrelevance). For example, Bazerman and Moore (2013) explained anchoring by presenting a study in which participants were asked to give an estimate date for the completion of the Taj Mahal, and their responses were influenced by irrelevant numbers that deliberately came to their minds (e.g., their phone numbers).

The above mentioned examples show how heuristics invoked by human brain may bias the decision making process. In the following paragraph, three main heuristic classes are described in more detail: (i) recognition; (ii) one-reason decision making; and (iii) trade-off. Gigerenzer and Gaissmeier (2011) define recognition-based decisions as such based on judgments on specifically recognized information while ignoring other cues. It includes simple recognition, fluency and take-the-first strategies. One can easily observe the application of this heuristic in daily life, as for choosing a meal in a restaurant people typically choose a widely familiar sirloin steak instead of a probably unknown “toad-in-the-hole” (a British dish made of sausage and Yorkshire pudding). Regarding sports, the results of Wimbledon tournament in 2004 were predicted more accurately by amateur players who knew only 50% of contestants as compared to Wimbledon experts (Serwe and Frings, 2006). Also, people tend to bet in a more popular team to win (or player to score). When asked to judge which of two cities is larger, respondents usually point out the one whose name sound more familiar (Gigerenzer, 1991).

Other studies covered successful German election predictions based exclusively on names' popularity as well as recognition-based stock portfolio building whose returns outpaced portfolios created by experts. By analyzing brand marketing, one can clearly notice that the whole concept of branding and promoting branded products is based on recognition. Fluency and take-the-first heuristics are derivatives of simple recognition and work as follows: fluency concerns choosing a faster recognized option out of two recognized, while take-the-first strategy, as the name suggests, consists of choosing the alternative that comes to one's mind the fastest. This phenomenon among other explains how team sportsmen take their blink-of-eye successful decisions (Johnson and Raab, 2003).

The second class of heuristics (one-reason) comprises strategies such as one-clever cue, hiatus heuristic and take-the-best heuristic. This class bases judgments on one good reason only, ignoring other cues (Gigerenzer and Gaissmaier, 2011). All strategies belonging to this class might appear similar at first, although they have some fundamental differences.

Summarizing and exemplifying them shortly, one-clever heuristic is applied for instance when baseball players or goalkeepers try to hit or catch approaching ball (expected trajectory is based on an heuristic rather than on real-time computing). In turn, take-the-best strategy (when comparing two options) includes ordering cues according to their relevance, stopping at the first that provides vivid differentiation and taking decision on that basis. For example, when choosing a restaurant between two alternatives, a tourist previously established a rank with a criteria for ranking the restaurants, with the following order of importance: (i) location, (ii) quality of meals, (iii) price level, (iv) interior design. If the location and the quality of meals do not differ significantly, as the restaurants are in the same neighborhood and both are ranked well in gastronomic guides, the tourist may focus on the first differencing cue (e.g., price level) and choose the restaurant with more attractive prices without paying any attention to the interior design.

The third group of heuristic comprises trade-off strategies. As the name suggests, these are multi-variable on-the-spot analyses which lead to criterion trade-offs. Following the example of choosing one of two restaurants, the decider would weight equally all of criteria and then compared available cues to make final decision. There two types of trade-off heuristics distinguished: tallying and 1/N rule. An interesting example of tallying was provided by McCammon and Haegeli (2007), who explained the phenomenon of this strategy by analyzing avoiding avalanche accidents. Avalanche experts listed seven cues appearing on the slope which usually accompany avalanche (e.g., the presence of water on the snow surface). When more than three cues are present, spending time on the slope is believed to pose a huge risk. Although the method seemed very straight forward, it predicted up to 92% of avalanches. The other trade-off strategy, 1/N rule, assumes allocation of resources equally to each of N alternatives (Gigerenzer and Gaissmaier, 2011). Regarding investing, it is worth to mention that the 1/N rule (portfolio value distributed equally to each instrument), beat the Markowitz mean-variance model in terms of returns (DeMiguel, Garlappi, and Uppal, 2009).

Apart from the above-mentioned heuristic classes, social intelligence stimulate efficient decision making (e.g., Sunstein, 2005). Examples of social intelligence include imitating successful behavior or tit-for-tat strategies. For the purpose of this research, social intelligence is omitted as heuristics type because of lower relevance regarding research methodology.

The next part of the literature review introduces concepts of stimulus-based and memory-based choices. As the name suggests, stimulus-based decision are impacted by stimuli which are present when a decision is being made, while memory-based choice requires deciders to maintain relevant options in working memory (Rottenreich et al., 2007). To better illustrate the differences between the two concepts, Lee (2002) provided the example of a travelling couple – for example, John and Betty – who had first driven through a newly discovered city and a few moments later was about to choose the restaurant for dinner. John tried to remember the signs and hoardings he saw on the way to the hotel, while Betty searched through tourist guides. This simple situation depicts the basic difference between the two concepts. John elicited the relevant options through his working memory (with no exposure to stimuli at the time decision taking) and Betty chose between different options when being exposed to a decision impacting stimuli. Another simple example concerns grocery shopping. Some customers prepare the list of products beforehand (memory-based) whereas others are more likely to make choices in-store when exposed to merchandising material and products visual appeal (stimulus-based). Rottenreich et al. (2007) put the concept of system 1 and system 2 though modes into the context of memory-based and stimulus-based choices. System 1 alludes to rapid and automatically taken decisions, in contrary to system 2, which include controlled, slow and deductive mental processing. The authors argue that memory-based choice tend to reflect relatively more system 1 processing, whereas stimulus-based choices reflect relatively more system 2 processing. This leads to differentiation of choice quality in these two types of decisions.

Apart from system 1 and 2 concepts, it is worth to mention explicit and implicit memory theories. These concepts shed new light on the memory-based and stimulus based-choices. Graf and Schacter (1985) coined the terms of implicit and explicit memory. According to them, the following mechanism can attributed to implicit memory: when trying to remember recently presented information, subjects are simply required to perform a task (stimulus); memory is revealed by a facilitation or change in task performance that is attributable to information acquired during a previous study episode, while explicit memory refers to revealing facts without external stimulation (conscious recollection of previously presented information). Examples that differ the mentioned types of memories is singing a song while not being able to remember specific parts of lyrics without melody (implicit memory), in contrary writing down the complete lyrics or poem alludes to explicit memory.

In this literature review section, we highlighted the concept of heuristics, explained some of the biases emanating from heuristics and mentioned heuristics as efficient tools for decision making. We also referred to stimulus-based and memory-based decisions and distinguished between implicit and explicit memory processing. Next, we describe the method for our study, which intended to compare the class of heuristic applied by respondents in both memory-based and stimulus-based choices.

Method

Participants were asked to complete an online survey on decision making. The sample size amounts to 205 participants (64.9% female), in their majority students of two Polish and two Portuguese Universities. They were some demographics and informed about the main purpose of the survey – including the fact that they should not check the answers in external sources. The mean age of participant amounted to 23.4 years and it ranged from 18 to 54. The respondents represented 28 countries in total, although the biggest fractions came from Poland (88 participants) and Portugal (35 participants).

The dependent variable was defined as the class of heuristic with three different values (recognition, one-reason decision and trade-off) which was analyzed separately in view of two independent variables which are decision type (memory-based and stimulus-based) as well as involvement level (high and low). Participants were asked to respond to eight questions. The questions comprised two types of decision. The first part (questions 1-4) included geography-related questions whereas the second part (questions 5-8) comprised investment decisions. The choice of question areas derived from the need of achieving different involvement from participants. We assumed that respondents were less involved when answering questions on geography (e.g., television show type) with no personal relevance and were more involved when answering questions on their personal investment choices. Moreover, the respondents were asked interchangeably to provide their choice on an actual issue (questions 1, 3, 5, 7) and then to justify how the choice was made (questions 2, 4, 6, 8). For example, participants were asked to name the largest city in a certain continent or decide on the most attractive investment options. However, after each of these questions, they were asked to choose which heuristic they used in their decision, by selecting a multiple choice option associated to each heuristic which were adapted to common language for the sake of easy understanding. Each stimulus-based choice from the same area was preceded by memory-based choice. The order was conditioned by the fact that the participants were supposed to reach their explicit memory first and then made a subsequent choice regarding a similar question but using the implicit memory framework.

The questionnaire assumed that the respondents were not sure about the right answer and this is why they were unconsciously forced to use heuristics. The questions on investment are the matter of personal choice, whereas geography questions have one correct answer which however is assumed to be unknown by respondents. The questionnaire was optimized in terms of time needed to fulfill it, so as not to be too distractive nor tedious. To avoid suggestive influence of multiple choice questions, each question was displayed separately.

Please see Table 1 for the questionnaire structure. As follows, regarding the geography questions, each one of the multiple choice questions is mapped to one heuristic, whereas for investment questions several questions are included in each heuristic type.

Table 1 – Questionnaire mapping

Type of question	Questionnaire reference	Heuristic type	Involvement
Geography questions	It simply came to my mind the fastest (e.g., I know quite a lot about this city; I traveled there often, etc...)	Recognition	Low
	I thought of one decisive factor (e.g., it has to be a big financial center OR it has to be a famous touristic destination)	One good reason	
	I came up with more than one criterion and compared their importance on the spot (e.g., financial center vs. famous touristic destination vs. capital city)	Trade-off	
	I knew the answer (for sure) beforehand	N/A	
Investment questions	It is the most popular way	Recognition	High
	I think the mechanisms behind it are the clearest to me		
	It has been proven by my friends or family		
	It is the least risky method	One good reason	
	It is featured by the highest return opportunities		
	It is featured by the best return to risk ratio	Trade-off	
There are some other features that influenced my decision			

Results

The purpose of this research was to compare the class of heuristic applied by respondents in memory-based and stimulus-based choices. Additionally, the survey design allowed the comparison between low-involvement and high-involvement decisions. The results are synthesized in the Table 2 (please note that the geography question excludes respondents who claimed to know the answer beforehand).

Table 2 – Descriptive analysis of results

	Memory-based		Stimulus-based	
Low involvement	Recognition	32%	Recognition	22%
	One good reason	26%	One good reason	34%
	Trade-off	42%	Trade-off	44%
High involvement	Recognition	35%	Recognition	39%
	One good reason	34%	One good reason	33%
	Trade-off	31%	Trade-off	28%

Regarding recognition heuristic, its application was the most frequent in stimulus-based high-involvement decision (39%) and the least frequent in stimulus-based low-involvement decision (22%). The one good reason heuristic application ranged from 26% in memory-based low-involvement choice to 34% in memory-based high-involvement choice. The trade-off heuristic was the lowest in stimulus-based high-involvement decision (28%) and the highest in stimulus-based low-involvement choice (44%).

Comparing heuristics used in memory-based and stimulus-based, one can notice that there were no coherent and significant differences between their applications. However, descriptive differences could be observed in application of the trade-off heuristic between low-involvement and high-involvement choices. The absolute average difference between memory-based and stimulus-based questions in application of recognition heuristic amounts to 9.9%, whereas regarding one-reason and trade-off strategies respectively 4.5% and 13.2%.

To analyze the statistical significance of results, a series of Chi-square tests were computed separately for each independent variable and each heuristic class frequency. Results revealed that Chi-square tests are in-line with the descriptive analysis, showing significant differences for high and low involvement questions regarding both the trade-off heuristic (Chi-square = 14.34, $df = 1$, $p < .01$) and the recognition heuristic (Chi-square = 8.44, $df = 1$, $p < .01$).

The above-shown results suggest that no significant differences were found in the application of heuristics between memory-based and stimulus-based choices, although significant differences were indeed found regarding low-involvement and high-involvement decisions.

Discussion

This study highlighted the relevance of heuristics as efficient decision making tools based on the heuristic classification of Gigerenzer and Gaissmaier (2011). We intended to shed some light into the mechanisms of heuristics and memory in human decision making. Although the obtained results do not confirm the research's hypothesis that stimulus-based and memory-based conditions would be related to the application of different heuristic classes, we found that the use of trade-off and recognition heuristics differ between low-involvement and high-involvement decisions.

Stimulus-based and memory-based choices seem not to be factors which influence the application of specific heuristics. This may be due to the fact that the choice applied heuristic is involvement-based, decider-based or simply situational problem-based rather than depending on usage of explicit and implicit memory. At this point, this study could draw attention to the fact that regarding decisions demanding higher involvement (e.g., personal investment preferences), deciders prefer to reach simple heuristic (recognition or social intelligence) rather than depending on personal judgment (which yielded on average a 10% higher usage rate) such as the analysis of cues which differentiate particular criteria.

Next, we highlight some insights of this research that, in our view, emerge for both consumer and investment decisions.

Insight 1 (consumer): Grocery shopping based in a pre-set list and in-store impulse decisions both rely on the use of the same type of heuristics.

As results showed that stimulus-based and memory-based choices reveal similar frequencies of heuristic type, this would imply that both quicker in-store shopping decision or more reflexive out of store decision would be influenced by similar heuristics. This insight is especially valuable for FMCG and other consumer goods companies which aim to influence shoppers' choices. Indeed, consumers' decision processing based on available cues is conducted similarity to situations when stimuli are not present. However, this does not mean that in-store decisions would be made without any impact of stimuli.

Insight 2 (investment): High-involvement investment decisions tend to be more dependent on recognition and social intelligence than simple low-involvement decisions.

Insight 3 (investment): Investment decisions based on direct stimuli are ruled by the same heuristics as decisions based on memory.

Similarly to consumer choices, investment decisions based on stimuli are subordinated to the same heuristic as memory-based choices. This emphasizes the interesting contribution for trading securities as well as marketing for financial products. High-involvement choices – specifically investment decisions – are highly affected by social intelligence which also brings value for banking and trading.

Limitations and suggestions for future research

This study is not without limitations. First of all, it assumes that respondents are aware of how they made decision and are able to consciously answer the question on how their choice was made. To some extent, the usage of heuristics is unconscious (Koehler, Brenner, and Griffin, 2002). The necessity to choose one's decision strategy may also imply that respondents would be more likely to choose the method which appear more complex and advanced to them (Marewski, 2010) (i.e., a cognitive bias emanating from overestimating their own decision complexity). Secondly, it is assumed that the sample (mainly composed of students) would represent the population. Another limitation is that participants, after answering the first multiple question in which different decision strategies are presented, they might try to adjust their next decisions to one of given strategies. Moreover, the survey does not analyze social intelligence as the separate decision strategy (social intelligence was included in recognition heuristics). This limitation was introduced in order to be able to compare different types of choices, both on geography (low-involvement) and investment (high involvement). Specifically, regarding the questions on geography, social intelligence heuristics are not applicable.

The question concerning other factors influencing chosen heuristics remains open. There are plenty of issues that could be subject of future research. More studies using different samples and participants from other countries, as cross-cultural variables might play a role in the use of heuristics. Also, future researchers could try to predict how human personality influences application of different heuristic classes. Another important issue would be to investigate heuristics in individual vs. social contexts, specifically related to the concepts of ownership and sharing (cf. Arsel, 2010) or predictors of public choice (cf. Wang, 2008). And, regarding leadership, it could be relevant to examine how the decision style of managers and leaders would impact their employees' class of used heuristics. This study aimed to shed some light into the role of heuristics in decision making.

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APPENDIX

Question 1

What is the largest city in Europe (in terms of population)?

Please give your best guess. Do not check any materials to answer the question.

Question 2

How have you decided regarding Question 1?

- a) I thought of one decisive factor (e.g., it has to be a big financial center OR it has to be a famous touristic destination.
- b) It simply came to my mind the fastest (e.g., I know quite a lot about this city; I traveled there often, etc.).
- c) I came up with more than one criterion and compared their importance on the spot (e.g., financial center vs. famous touristic destination vs. capital city, etc.).
- d) I did not guess; I knew the answer for sure beforehand.

Question 3

Which of the following cities do you consider to be the largest city in Asia (in terms of population)?

- a) Seul
- b) Karachi
- c) Tokyo
- d) Jakarta
- e) Beijing
- f) Mumbai
- g) Shanghai

Question 4

How have you decided regarding Question 3?

- a) I thought of one decisive factor (e.g., it has to be a big financial center OR it has to be a famous touristic destination.
- b) It simply came to my mind the fastest (e.g., I know quite a lot about this city; I traveled there often, etc.).
- c) I came up with more than one criterion and compared their importance on the spot (e.g., financial center vs. famous touristic destination vs. capital city, etc.).
- d) I did not guess; I knew the answer for sure beforehand.

Question 5

Imagine that you possess significant savings. You do not want to spend them now. How would you invest them?

Please give a short one-line description or simply the name of the financial instrument.

Question 6

How have you decided regarding Question 5?

- a) It is the most popular way.
- b) I think the mechanisms behind it are the clearest to me.
- c) It has been recommended by my family or friends.
- d) It is the least risky method.
- e) It is featured by the highest return opportunities.
- f) It is featured by the best return to risk ratio.
- g) There are some other features which influenced my decision.

Question 7

Which of the following investment options appeals to you the most?

Please choose the one that you find the most attractive.

- a) Bank deposit.
- b) Treasury Bonds.
- c) Investment in stocks (single or portfolio-based).
- d) Options (regarding all types/strategies).
- e) Corporate Bonds.
- f) Real estate.
- g) Alternative investments.

Question 8

How have you decided regarding Question 7?

- a) It is the most popular way.
- b) I think the mechanisms behind it are the clearest to me.
- c) It has been recommended by my family or friends.
- d) It is the least risky method.
- e) It is featured by the highest return opportunities.
- f) It is featured by the best return to risk ratio.
- g) There are some other features which influenced my decision.